

PROCESSING PARAMETERS FOR CMC MATERIALS USING YAG LASER

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ABSTRACT.

A pulsed Nd-YAG laser has been used to machine three different examples of Ceramic Matrix Composite, CMC. In each case the reinforcing fibre is silicon carbide, SiC whilst the matrices are respectively a borosilicate glass, a magnesium-alumino-silicate glass-ceramic and a Chemical Vapour Infiltrated (CVI) silicon carbide. The systematic study has been performed with respect to both material removal rate and quality of surface produced, such that comparison of the trials on these specific materials has permitted an initial analysis of the suitability of YAG lasers for processing CMC systems in general.

INTRODUCTION.

Composite ceramic systems are currently the subject of a great deal of research as a solution to the problem of brittle failure associated with monolithics. This major obstacle to the widespread exploitation of ceramics, particularly for high temperature structural applications, may be solved by such systems but if anything they increase the difficulty of producing component forms. Commercially, the machining of ceramics is still largely limited to diamond grinding. As well as being costly and time-consuming this is extremely restricted in suitable geometry and may introduce substantial damage into the material. Although near-net shaping techniques such as Chemical Vapour Infiltration (CVI) reduce these problems, the lack of a faster and cheaper method of machining ceramic materials must be regarded a significant hurdle to their full utilisation as engineering materials. The use of lasers have been considered as a possible answer. The principal benefits include the wholly non-contacting nature of the process (no tool wear, no mechanical stresses imposed on workpiece), and the fact that it is capable of sophisticated geometrical manipulation using CAM techniques. The main problem stems from the extreme thermal input of the process and the behaviour of materials that are generically refractory in nature.

There is therefore a great deal of interest in the factors that may contribute to the successful processing of CMC materials in general using lasers. The approach that has been adopted in this work is to specify a single *type* of laser (to limit the incident radiation to a single wavelength and thus the material/laser coupling considerations to a single case) and to systematically investigate the processing of three different material compositions that between them may be considered representative of the range of CMC systems. The trials have been formulated and performed with

the express intention of comparison across the range of CMC compositions with the aim that the factors contributing to any determined results may be applied to other compositional variations.

MATERIALS STUDIED AND LASER CONFIGURATION.

The three matrix phases are a borosilicate glass (very similar to commercially available Pyrex™, producing a *Glass-Matrix Composite*, GMC), a Magnesium-Alumino-Silicate (MAS, *Glass-Ceramic Matrix Composite* or GCMC) and Chemical Vapour Infiltrated SiC (resulting in a true *Ceramic Matrix Composite*, CMC). A common factor with all three materials is Nippon Carbon's Nicalon™ 201-grade silicon carbide fibre, used as the reinforcing phase in each case. In the first two materials, this was coated with a slurry of the matrix material and filament wound into unidirectional sheets. A number of such pre-pregs are laid-up in alternate 0-90° layers and hot pressed to form a plaque. In the case of the SiC-SiC material, the fibre was supplied in a cross-weave mat, a number of lay-ups of which were 'filled' with the matrix phase by Chemical Vapour Infiltration (CVI). Most of the trials have been performed on plaques of the respective composites approximately 3mm thick, although thicker and thinner specimens have also been investigated, principally to determine the maximum speed at which various thicknesses may be processed.

All of the trial sets have been performed with the Lumonics JK701 pulsed Nd-YAG laser, used in the (Low Divergence) LD2 Resonator arrangement. An 80mm focal length cemented achromat was used for the final stage lens. The JK701 has an internal power meter, but this takes its measurement from a point just after the resonator and before the final optic train, including the Beam Expansion Telescope (BET) and the final lens. In addition, at extremes of adjustment it is possible to produce 'clipping' of the beam by the nozzle assembly, so an external power meter - a water-cooled Coherent 'Fieldmaster' was used to verify the internal meter's reading or evaluate the power losses occurring in the final optical stages. A custom-built nozzle assembly has been manufactured that facilitates nozzle alignment, allows rapid access to replace marked or damaged cover-glasses as well as permitting full adjustment of nozzle stand-off distance independently of focus position for trials involving changing the focal-point-to-surface distance, assist gas variations etc. This has made adjustment of the laser set-up an easier task than would be required if the equipment were used for a standard industrial application. Positioning of the workpiece was achieved by the use of a Unidex 400 CNC controller connected to a 3-axis workstation. This fully-programmable facility allows 600x600x300mm of accurate and repeatable travel, facilitating the duplicating of test geometries on different specimens.

Oxygen, nitrogen and argon were investigated as choices of assist gas. These were manifolded to allow a maximum supply pressure of approximately 8bar, measured from a point close to the nozzle orifice.

RESULTS OF TEST PROGRAMME.

The programme of work in this study has examined many laser parameter variations, some of which relate more directly to the performance characteristics of the particular laser configuration used. The primary concerns of the material study, however, are the questions of laser penetration, maximum permissible speed of processing and the resulting quality or degree of damage induced in the cut surface. To determine the first of these, a number of tests were performed on each material type in which the principle pulse parameters of energy, duration (or pulse width) and repetition rate were ranged within the tuned condition of the LD2 resonator. By these variations, the resulting average and peak powers of the incident beam were investigated. The laser's tuning

constraints do not permit all three parameters to be varied completely independently, so in many instances, the effects of the pulse repetition rate were isolated by comparing the penetrative capabilities of *single shots* of the laser. It was determined that for a constant point of focus and beam expansion (power density), the geometry of the blind holes produced was quite consistent and thus sectioning the holes and measuring their depth gives a simplified but effective indication of the relative material removal efficiency. When each material is considered separately, the penetration is not surprisingly found to increase when greater peak powers are employed. Of greater interest is a comparison of the results of the three composites together. The depth of penetration is plotted against peak power for each of the materials in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Peak Power vs. Hole Depth for the three materials studied.

There is clearly a substantial difference in the response of the three separate materials to the laser. There is typically a 40-50% increase in penetration obtained with the MAS matrix material when compared with the glass matrix, and an even greater improvement with the SiC/SiC material, in some instances as high as 90%. As all of the materials contain the same fibre reinforcement phase ie SiC fibre, this raises a question concerning the relative 'machinability' of the three matrix phases. The laser emits a coherent beam of light of 1.06µm wavelength and the extent to which various materials absorb and react to such a discrete form of energy differs. Trials were performed on monolithic samples of the three matrix materials and confirmed that there is a high discrepancy in the coupling characteristics in these cases. The Pyrex material is in fact almost completely transparent to the YAG laser, to the extent that it may not be processed at all as a monolithic material. The laser may sometimes couple with impurities in the glass, but as the rest of the material is unaffected this simply results in brittle cracking as the bulk of the glass is unable to accommodate the thermal expansion. The MAS material does couple successfully with the laser, in fact every bit as well as the SiC monolithic. It would seem, therefore that the processing of the Pyrex matrix material is achieved by the conduction of heat from the absorbing SiC fibre phase to the matrix glass. The difference in the penetration of the MAS and the SiC matrix materials may be as a result of better matching of thermal properties in the case of the SiC/SiC composite.

The maximum cut speed attainable for each material over a range of plaque thicknesses reflects the conclusion concerning the relative coupling of each composite. Figure 2 shows the results for the three materials.

Figure 2. Maximum cut speed at 3.5kW for various thicknesses of the three materials.

Generally, the cut speed trials show that as the material thickness increases, the maximum speed of cut for full penetration is reduced, but in a nominally hyperbolic nature rather than linear. This may be a result of the influence of heat flow within the plaques during continuous cutting. In the thinnest plates, this will have a significant 'pre-heating' effect, which may aid the cutting process [1]. The greater degree of coupling of the SiC/SiC material is reflected by an overall increase in the maximum cut speed. It should be noted, however, that the maximum speed recorded for the thinnest specimens was limited not by the penetrative capabilities of the laser at the elevated speed, but by the pulse repetition rate at the tuned condition. The value recorded is the speed at which the cut ceased to be continuous and became a perforated line due to the cut speed exceeding the overlap of the individual pulses. This emphasises a characteristic of using a pulsed laser for continuous cutting operations at speed.

Depth of focus investigations were initially performed due to the surface characteristics of the composite plaques. The processing methods for these materials, notably the SiC/SiC composite produce a sheet material that does not have a very even surface. This raises the question of whether surface undulations, which will locally vary the point of focus of the laser beam and indirectly, the power density, will adversely affect the processing. The results obtained from each material confirm that the penetration of the material is not sensitive to the point of focus varying within $\pm 2\text{mm}$ of the material surface, but this does have an interesting effect upon the shape of the hole. In each case, the hole is convergently tapered at the extremes of focus, +5mm and -5mm with respect to the material surface, but divergent at 0mm. This phenomena is shown for the case of the borosilicate matrix GMC in Figure 3, (a) and (b). Despite a similar effect being noticed in the processing of other materials [2], a satisfactory explanation for this finding (other than it being a result of internal reflections in the hole) has not been determined. This has a significant implication for the maximum attainable cut speed for the materials. As has been observed during the cutting trials, the speed at which the thinner plaques are processed is limited by the separation of the individual pulses to produce a perforated, rather than continuous cut. Any attempts to produce a larger hole and therefore greater permissible distance between pulses to produce a continuous kerf will incur penalties in terms of power density and therefore penetrative

capabilities. This problem may only be minimised for given pulse parameters by ensuring that the individual holes produced are as parallel as possible, thus avoiding a perforated cut across the entire material section. The focusing criteria to achieve this condition has been found to vary for the three materials studied as well as for different thicknesses of the same material but it is often the case that a focus point coincident with the top surface of the material does not produce a parallel-sided kerf. This will unnecessarily limit the speed at which a through cut may be achieved. As an example, the optimum focal position when cutting a 2mm thick plaque of the MAS - matrix composite was determined to be at the mid-point, 1mm below the surface. Figure 4 shows a plot of the entry and exit kerf width obtained in this case with the point of focus of the laser beam varying between ± 5 mm with respect to the material surface.

Figure 3. Depth of focus trials on GMC material; (a) Beam focused 5mm below material surface, and (b) beam focused at material surface.

Figure 4. Variation in kerf geometry with focal point. 2mm thick MAS GCMC. 3.5kW, 5bar N₂ gas assist.

The emphasis of the remaining tests was to examine the quality of the cut surfaces rather than the material removal rate. Most significant of these were the trials using different assist gases. Four examples were tried, nitrogen, argon, oxygen and air. A substantial difference in the results was noted between the various materials. The glass matrix material is very susceptible to oxidative degradation, to the extent that none of the assist gases were able to exclude the ambient atmosphere sufficiently to stop the generation of a silicate glass 'dross', particularly evident on the underside of the cut. When oxygen was used, the build-up of this material was sufficient to partially re-seal the cut. Subsequent separation of the surfaces broke this glass and exposed debonded fibres. The nitrogen and argon did reduce this substantially however, the resulting cut surface being quite generally acceptable. An interesting result was achieved using air. It had been speculated that the oxygen content of the air may be absorbed by the most reactive molten/vaporised material and subsequently be ejected from the cut along with the process debris. This would then leave a predominantly nitrogen-rich atmosphere to 'flush' the surface of the bulk material. This was found to be the case when the tests were examined. The air-assisted cut was very similar to the inert gas examples, again producing an acceptable cut that may, depending upon requirements benefit from a 'deburring' operation to remove the remnants of the ejected dross.

The cut surfaces of the MAS composite were similar to those of the Pyrex, but to a lesser degree, reflecting the greater stability of the crystallised matrix to an oxidising environment. None of the cuts re-sealed, but there were still significant deposits of alumino-silicate glass on the processed surface when oxygen was used. This was typically observed in the form of a bimodal distribution of quite spherical particles in the ranges 2-5 μm and 10-15 μm , as shown in Figure 5. Once again, the use of air proved to be an economic alternative to nitrogen or argon, with only a slight drop in cut quality.

Figure 5. Cut surface produced in MAS-matrix material at 80mm/min., 3.5kW and using 4bar O₂ gas assist.

The results obtained from the SiC/SiC material were a significant improvement. The nitrogen, argon and air produced particularly clean cuts (with, as before, a slight degradation when using air), but even the oxygen cut surface did not show excessive silicate deposits. It should be mentioned that in the case of this material, there may be an advantage to generating a thin layer of

glass. The material depends upon the bonding of the matrix to the fibres for many of its physical properties, and this is enhanced by microstructurally engineering a deposited layer of pure carbon on the surface of the fibres [3,4]. This sub-micron layer is *particularly* susceptible to oxidation, and so the material is usually sealed by a layer of glass as a final manufacturing step to prevent the ingress of oxygen to the interfacial layer. Cutting the material exposes the carbon layer, and so the generation of a silicate glass (if it could be shown to inhibit the diffusion of atmospheric oxygen at high temperatures) could be a distinct advantage.

CONCLUSIONS.

The use of a pulsed, Nd-YAG laser to process three related but significantly different glass and ceramic matrix composites has been demonstrated. Consideration has been given to both the laser's ability to penetrate the material in different configurations and the resulting processed surface quality.

The degree of scatter of the data is significant, typically 10% of the measured penetration. The explanation for this is in the homogeneity of the composite plaques. Measurements made on the two hot-pressed material compositions (the borosilicate GMC and the MAS GCMC) after processing give a value of approximately 30-35vol.% for the fibre content, but due to the method of production, local variations are estimated to lie within the range 20-65vol.%. The SiC/SiC material does not have such a high variation as the fibre is supplied as a pre-woven mat, but this material shows a significant amount of porosity (the material is not fabricated under pressure) and once again, this disrupts the homogeneity. As the local fibre content is the determining factor in the processing of the glass matrix material and the laser does not couple with voids in the SiC/SiC composite, these processing variations could well account for the scatter in data. These features should, however, be regarded as a characteristic of these and similar materials.

Whilst the material removal rate for a given composite is primarily dependant on the peak power of the laser, the material itself is a significant factor. Certain structures are simply transparent to the laser energy's wavelength of 1.06 μm . This is the case with certain borosilicate (Pyrex) compositions. The effect of this has repercussions for the quality of the processed surface as well, as the removal of these phases depends upon the conduction of heat from a phase that *does* absorb the laser energy. As this is necessarily achieved with a limited efficiency, the cut surface shows more evidence of redeposited and molten material. Fortunately, silicon carbide (which is most commonly used for fibres in these composites) absorbs this wavelength particularly well.

Of the materials tested, the most promising results were obtained from the SiC/SiC composite material. Despite the porosity shown by this composite, it couples with the laser energy more completely than either the Pyrex or MAS matrices, and it has significantly less susceptibility to oxidation at high temperatures, resulting in a particularly clean cut surface.

Although the type and pressure of the gas assist does not seem to influence the rate of material removal significantly, it does have an overriding effect on the quality of the processed surface. Most of the materials are, to varying degrees subject to oxidation at high temperatures. In the case of silicate compositions, the use of oxygen as an assist gas is to be avoided. Large volumes of silicate glass are generated, which may partially or completely re-seal the cut. More acceptable results are obtained from the use of nitrogen or argon (ie gases with which the material does not readily react at high temperatures), but in the cases tried, air may be recommended as an economic alternative. Once again, this depends on the specific requirements of the process, as there is a slight degradation in the cut quality.

A principal finding of these studies has been that although various fibre and matrix combinations may be processed quite successfully using a YAG laser, the absorption characteristics of *both* phases have a significant influence upon the efficiency of the material removal and the quality of the cut surface. The *relative* coupling efficiencies of the constituents should therefore be considered when attempting to optimise both speed and quality of processing. Recent microstructural developments have optimised the mechanical behaviour of certain glass and ceramic composites by selecting a matrix phase that possesses a similar thermal expansion coefficient to that of the fibre [5]. By extending this criteria to the absorption characteristics, it should be possible to create CMC materials that may be economically processed by laser techniques with a minimum of machining damage.

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